

Our world is becoming dependent on cyber-physical systems (CPS). This provides unprecedented innovation opportunities, but also represents unprecedented complexity. We need to design future CPS to make sure that they become human-centred and part of a circular economy.

Towards a living dimension: the future of cyber-physical systems

By FRANCESCA PALUMBO, RAQUEL LAZCANO and DANIEL MADROÑAL

Over the last few years, society has been drastically affected by the COVID-19 pandemic and other major events, such as the war in Ukraine. The whole world has been affected by these events and, subsequently, technology is also on the verge of a (yet another) revolution.

Without doubt, humans have gained a central role in information and communication technology systems and are requiring these systems to be more advanced and autonomous than ever. But is it just a matter of having humans at the centre of technology, or is the actual human-system relationship going to change? Are systems ready to team up with humans in a living dimension, creating a new form of society? More importantly, if not, how will they need to evolve to achieve this?

Key insights

- Expectations regarding CPS have changed: CPS are moving towards a living dimension. Future CPS will become capable of collaborating with humans towards a common goal, blurring the boundaries between CPS and humans.
- Classic CPS see humans mostly as operators or the physical process to be controlled. Several issues need to be addressed in order for humans and CPS to form part of the same society.
- The key enabling technologies required to power a new generation of CPS are as follows: artificial intelligence (AI), swarm intelligence, the tactile internet, and the computing continuum. These enabling technologies will contribute to increased decision-making and coordination capabilities of future CPS.
- Challenges include aspects relating to modelling, architectures, design, and security. These are already intrinsic challenges of this domain, and which are now exacerbated by the living dimension and the presence of the humans at the centre of the paradigm.
- By definition, future CPS will be increasingly autonomous and will be of an evolvable nature, aspects that generate significant challenges for CPS scientists.

Key recommendations

- Prioritize research on AI following an integral strategy. AI at the edge and cloud intelligence should be effectively brought together to allow rapid feedback processing and independent single element evolution, while maintaining the full picture.
- Exploit AI to make models flexible enough to encompass for post-deployment system evolution to cope with emergent situations and to adapt to unpredictable human behaviours.
- Develop new low-latency, multi-modal, reliable communication architectures following the tactile internet paradigm to allow overcoming human-to-system traditional command-based interaction and achieve a more natural peer-to-peer seamless interaction.
- Continue investing in swarm intelligence studies and begin testing embodied CPS swarms in complex large-scale, realistic environments with a high degree of heterogeneity to put the basis for forming a heterogeneous society of CPS collaborating with humans.
- Extend threat modelling for embodied swarm-based CPS systems tackling the needs and effectively protecting the heterogeneous society formed of humans and CPS influencing each other.
- Leverage and research on effective interoperability of existing design frameworks, considering humans at every stage of CPS design, and ensuring there is continuous verification of system properties during the design process.

Human-triggered technological shift

Over the last few years, the world has witnessed major events including the escalating impact of the climate change, the war in Ukraine and the COVID-19 pandemic. The full impact of these events on life in general, and in technology in particular, remains to be seen.

Taking the COVID-19 pandemic as an example, it has already had an impact on human lives, supply chains, work, and markets. Forced social distancing and a significant reduction of human presence on work sites resulted in major investments in tools to support remote work and monitor industry verticals (e.g. manufacturing, transportation and logistics).

This, in turn, has led to extreme digitalization and virtualization that, in the information and communication technology (ICT) domain, is the continuation of a journey started decades ago. Terms like disappearing computers, ubiquitous computing and ubiquitous information, pervasive computing, embedded systems and “smart anything everywhere” are in common use today. The mobile internet has been flanked by the internet of things (IoT) and, as discussed later in this article, the tactile internet is just around the corner.

All of this points to a new technology revolution, where the computing domain is so entangled with humans that a new paradigm is necessary to redefine this relationship. Multiple examples can be found in our daily lives, hinting at a not-so-distant future where the pervasive usage of

cyber-physical systems (CPS) and human-computer interaction reach unprecedented levels: autonomous driving, smart cities or remote and virtualized healthcare, to name just a few.

The flagship of all these examples, the one that entangles all of them simultaneously, is the so-called *metaverse*. While the term was first used in 1992, recently it has gained significant momentum, since it has started to be closer to a reality than a chimera. Although a single definition has yet to be agreed upon in the literature, it can be defined as “an integrated immersive ecosystem where the barriers between the virtual and real worlds are seamless to users, allowing the use of avatars and holograms to work, interact and socialize via simulated shared experience” [1].

While this is just one example illustrating where the technology is going and what a possible future for CPS could look like, it highlights many of the issues we have mentioned: CPS, now more than ever, are human-centred. They form the basis of the creation of a virtual and remote community where humans can interact, work and, eventually, live.

However, although “futuristic” concepts such as the metaverse are now closer than ever, the technology in general, and CPS in particular, still need to evolve before such a future becomes attainable. This evolution needs to take place not only from the scientific perspective, but also from the societal one, where many issues are appearing as a result of an ever more digitalized society [2]. As mentioned above, a new paradigm

is emerging, one that will revolutionize the way CPS are defined, modelled and realized, and one that needs to respond to these many issues.

In this article, we present our vision of how classic CPS, through some key enabling technologies (KETs), will evolve in order to cope with a future where the borders between cyber and physical parts will be more blurred than ever, reshaping their definition and paving the way towards a *new paradigm where CPS will have a living dimension and will not only interact with humans, but team up with them in a new form of society*.

Classic cyber-physical systems

In 2017, the United States National Science Foundation (NSF) Cyber Physical Systems Group defined CPS as “engineered systems that are built from, and depend upon, the seamless integration of computational algorithms and physical components” [3].

As depicted in **Figure 1**, CPS are closed-control loop systems, where the physical part, representing the environment, is observed through sensors. Observations are then used by the cyber part, which processes the information gathered to control and/or provide feedback to the physical part by means of actuators and/or proper interfaces. Sensors and actuators represent the boundaries, crossed by data only, between the physical and the cyber parts.

Data can be processed/stored at the edge or in the cloud. Processing/control is typi-

Figure 1: CPS overview (authors’ art)

cally smart, although this does not necessarily imply artificial intelligence (AI); smartness can also be achieved through runtime modelling and prediction techniques to understand the current physical system condition and to react appropriately, adjusting (when and where needed) the computation and/or providing a different service.

Today, the cyber part is rarely a monolithic computing item. Indeed, it is more often composed of interconnected processing units. Therefore, the network fabric and connectivity devices play a key role in the cyber part of the CPS.

Often CPS are described in terms of views or layers, namely:

- *physical* – the environment/process that the CPS controls;
- *computational (or functional)* – the composition of the system in terms of computing resources and the algorithms executed;
- *communication (or network)* – interaction among components and exchange with the physical environment.

Going back to the NSF definition, it continues as follows: “*Advances in CPS will enable capability, adaptability, scalability, resiliency, safety, security, and usability that will far exceed the simple embedded systems of today. CPS technology will transform the way people interact with engineered systems – just as the Internet has transformed the way people interact with information.*”

The CPS available today have certainly made good on this promise. Nevertheless,

expectations for the role of humans now go far beyond simple interaction.

Humans in CPS have been always seen either as operators or as the controlled physical system. Steps to bring humans closer to machinery have already been taken in the manufacturing sector with the concept of human-CPS (HCPS) that emerged thanks to advances in IoT and AI combined with CPS. However, the role of a human in HCPS, according to the authors of [4], is still seen as the master (the creators, managers, and operators of intelligent machines) rather than a teammate.

Now, the aim is for humans to act as partners of the CPS in the realization of a common goal. This poses some challenges:

- It is difficult to predict human behaviour and model human decisions. Indeed, starting from an initial assumption, the system will have to learn and adjust as it is used, in order to adapt to mutable human will.
- Dependability issues become more severe: in addition to protecting sensitive data, guaranteeing their privacy and security, safety mechanisms should also be present.

Addressing these challenges will bring CPS towards a new living dimension. The market, accelerated by the many verticals demanding effective system/process virtualization and autonomy, is pushing for this, and it is extremely dynamic. According to a recent analysis by Data Bridge Market Research [5], it will reach more than US\$ 12 million by 2028, with a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of more than 10% each year.

Increased penetration of the internet and AI are essential enablers for this market and will contribute, in our vision, to extend the NSF classic CPS definition as follows: **increased decision-making and coordination capabilities will make it possible for future generations of CPS to autonomously collaborate with their human teammates and with each other. They will form a kind of society with unprecedented cognitive and coordination capabilities, taking an additional step forward in the way people interact with engineered systems and blurring the boundaries between the CPS and its operators.**

Key enabling technologies

Future CPS with a living dimension will be an evolution of classic CPS. They will be smart systems capable of making decisions in an autonomous manner, interacting with human beings, and collaborating as a group among each other and with humans. This expected evolution of CPS will undoubtedly be determined by the two major market drivers: connectivity and AI.

In our vision, four main KETs are driving this revolution: on the one hand, AI for decision making, the tactile internet for interaction, and swarm intelligence for collaboration; on the other hand, the computing continuum, which is both an enabler and a requirement to bring all the aforementioned functionalities together.

Artificial intelligence

The global AI market size was valued at US\$ 93.5 billion in 2021 and is projected to expand at a CAGR of 38.1% from 2022 to

Figure 2: Virtual and physical worlds in AI [10]

2030 [6]. Research and innovation directed by tech giants including, among others, Google, Microsoft, Apple, and IBM, are driving the adoption of advanced technologies in industry verticals, such as automotive, healthcare, and manufacturing. For instance, following the acquisition of the Mobileye autonomous vehicle business in 2017 and of the AI chipmaker Habana in 2019, Intel Corporation has acquired also Cnvr.io and SigOpt, providing a platform for data scientists to build, train, compare and run machine learning models and an optimization platform to run models and simulations.

These acquisitions testify to the fact that remaining competitive in the market of next-generation chips is not just a matter of pushing a new efficient architecture onto the market, but also requires investment in tools for customers to support the definition of the loads running on the new chips.

AI-enabled CPS are systems that, generally speaking, adopt some kind of intelligence somewhere in the product, meaning either at the *virtual* and/or at the *physical* level, as shown in Figure 2 which depicts different crosscutting virtual technologies (on the left) applicable to various physical systems and application domains (on the right).

For example:

- AI controllers (e.g. based on supervised learning and reinforcement learning) are virtual enabling technologies to be used in place of more traditional controllers (e.g. based on proportional integral derivative control or model predictive control) to control physical processes [7].
- Deep reinforcement learning methodologies are virtual enablers for physical autonomous indoor navigation systems [8].
- On physical factory floors, the use of smart machinery relying on advanced human-machine interfaces, based on virtual AI-enabling technologies such as speech recognition, might dramatically improve the safety of machine operators [9].

There is undoubtedly plenty of hype around AI. According to a recent study focused on AI-enabled CPS in the chemical domain [11], in the last 10 years the keywords “*cyber-physical system*” and “*artificial intelligence*” have been combined in 447 articles. Between the years 2019 and 2021, a significant increase in publications occurred in this area, accounting for 71% of the total publications on this topic in the last 10 years.

There has been also a proliferation of models for AI applications. New, more accurate models are proposed every year. Nevertheless, such increased accuracy generally does not come for free: network size and corresponding computational costs might be extremely high as well, as depicted in Figure 3 [12].

Figure 3: Accuracy versus complexity in ImageNet Top-1 network implementations [12]

AI has given rise to new challenges on how to efficiently deploy those demanding networks on diverse hardware platforms to meet different hardware efficiency constraints (e.g. latency or energy). The many challenges AI faces towards sustainability are thoroughly analysed in the 2021 HiPEAC Vision [2], where special attention is given to the growing ecological costs of AI versus the potential ecological benefits, such as those brought about by fields as smart agriculture.

The interaction of CPS and the environment allows these systems to obtain many useful data, which could potentially improve the knowledge the system has of the environment, steering positive behaviours, actions and control over it. Nevertheless, the availability of data does not automatically entail the ability to understand. This is where AI represents an unquestionably powerful instrument to boost data reasoning.

Tactile internet

The number of IoT devices worldwide is expected to increase from 9.7 billion in 2020 to more than 29 billion in 2030. Such devices are used in all types of verticals, with the consumer accounting for 60% in 2020 [13]. With these numbers in mind, it is clear how the collective ability to share information and cooperate has become extremely high.

The mobile internet gave people the opportunity to exchange data and multimedia content on the move. Next, IoT-enabled networking smart devices resulted in collections of interconnected computing devices constantly exchanging data.

The new frontier is known as the tactile internet [14][15]. It intends to enable the “control of the IoT in real time, also adding a new dimension to human-to-machine interaction by enabling tactile and haptic sensations”. With the shift of ICT infrastructures towards the edge, it is understandable how the role of the network is of paramount

importance. Speed, capacity, bandwidth, throughput, security, resiliency and low latency, already factors under scrutiny with the emergence of the IoT, are becoming increasingly important as the tactile internet gains momentum.

In many cases, tactile internet scenarios have the characteristics of CPS. A representative example of a tactile internet application with all the key CPS ingredients would be a remote surgery operation [16]:

- Humans are in the loop representing, respectively, the operator (the surgeon) and the physical view (the patient) of the CPS.
- The scenario is characterized by dynamic and reactive behaviours. Bidirectional haptic communications are intended to guarantee real-time exchanges of the control commands, coming from the operator, and the haptic feedback, from the teleoperator robot. Based on the latter, operator decisions can change and, consequently, the robot set-up can also be adjusted.
- A reliable networking infrastructure represents the communication layer, and dedicated edge-based computing architectures support smart real time processing on both the operator and patient sides.

Bearing in mind that all the requirements for IoT (such as guaranteed availability, the coexistence of different media, and security) still stand, on top of the aforementioned CPS-oriented characteristics, the tactile internet imposes also [16, 17]:

- Hard real-time processing.
- Ultra-low latency with a round trip in the order of 1 ms.
- High reliability, normally indicated by a very low failure rate (10^{-3} to 10^{-7}).
- Multi-modal bilateral communications, including visual, auditory and haptic feedback.

Allowing humans to be part of the system itself and not restraining them to giving commands and receiving an output would boost human-machine interaction possibilities. Following the tactile internet paradigm, these interactions are evolving towards a safe, reliable and effective human-to-CPS peer-to-peer relationship, unlocking their collaboration within the same working area or even from distant locations. AI at the edge is necessary to achieve the ultra-low latency imposed by the tactile internet, performing on-the-fly predictions of the expected action/reaction and refining the stimulus once the real data arrives.

Swarm intelligence

In nature, swarms are groups of individuals that coordinate among each other to meet a global goal, typically unreachable by a stand-alone entity. Swarm members

© Adobe Stock

follow a set of relatively simple rules and interact locally with other individuals and with their environment. Swarm intelligence exploits the understanding of the conditions, rules and interaction patterns defining swarm behaviour to design artificial systems exhibiting effective swarm behaviours [18].

Traditionally, swarm intelligence has been largely adopted to design successful algorithms for optimization, networking, and decision-making problems, as in the case of particle swarm optimization (PSO) [19] and ant colony optimization (ACO) [20]. More recently, the concept of swarm robotics has emerged. This uses relatively simple, physically embodied agents to accomplish the given swarm mission in many different contexts, including marine applications (see for example Apium Swarm Robotics [21]) or smart agriculture (see for example SwarmFarm Robotics [22]).

The market of swarm-intelligence-based systems was valued at US\$ 21 million in 2021 and is expected to register a CAGR of over 37% during the period 2021-2026 [23]. So far, the major driver for this market has proved to be the ability of swarm intelligence to help solve complex optimization problems (i.e. moving goods while minimizing operational costs and travel time, or enabling business teams to generate highly accurate financial forecasts). The adoption of embodied swarms in critical missions is becoming another major contributor to the growth of this market, especially in the United States, due to the increased adoption of swarm-based drones in defence [24].

A collection of cooperative embodied robots is a swarm if it exhibits the following abilities:

- **adaptability:** it can adapt to dynamic environments and cope with different tasks;
- **robustness:** it can cope with disturbances and failures, such as the loss or the malfunctioning of individual agents;
- **scalability:** it performs well with varying numbers of swarm members and varying problem sizes.

© Adobe Stock

The number or density of agents plays an important role in swarm performance. A swarm system cannot operate below a given critical mass, which is the minimum number of elements for the cooperation to give positive effects.

Finally, swarms are expected to present super-linear performance scaling: the effect of the overall system is required to be more than the sum of the effects of its individual parts. If the synergies of cooperation boost each individual swarm members' performance, then the overall system is a well-designed swarm. This phenomenon is known as the "swarm effect" and it means that, within the bounds of feasible swarm sizes, not only the efficiency of the whole swarm as a group, but also the efficiency of each individual should increase.

As discussed in [25], embodied swarms and CPS resemble each other. Indeed, a CPS can be composed of distributed elements, composed of subsystems presenting local coordination and exposing partial autonomy. They can leverage distributed control, supervision and management and can be capable of (self-)reconfiguration at different timescales.

These characteristics allow both the evolution of the overall system during its operation and the emergence of useful behaviours. Clearly, for a CPS to be classified as a swarm it should also respond and adapt to changing conditions, in a robust

and scalable manner, and its mission should be accomplished by harnessing the local cooperation of its individual composing elements thanks to the swarm effect.

Including the swarm intelligence concept in a system composed of CPS that understand their environment thanks to AI and that can interact with humans thanks to the tactile internet concept completes the system with a sense of society and collaboration capabilities. Having (partially) autonomous, highly distributed and cooperating CPS collaborating with humans would result in superlinear performance improvements for the system, as long as the provision of swarm intelligence is part of system design from the outset.

Computing continuum: from edge to cloud and vice-versa

Edge computing is defined as the *ability to process data close to sensors*. Processing takes place locally instead of transporting raw data to the cloud or to remote data centres. According to the International Data Corporation, by the end of 2023 more than half of new enterprises' ICT infra-

structure will be at the edge [26], while Gartner has predicted that, by 2025, 75% of enterprise-generated data will be created and processed outside a traditional data centre or cloud [27].

There are many widely acknowledged advantages associated with edge processing:

- reduction in response latency (data-to-result processing time), saving both the time required to transmit the data and the time required to receive the result;
- savings in bandwidth, energy and costs related to data transfer, as well as the cost of storing the raw data, which can be larger than the processed results;
- increased system robustness to network failures, reducing the occurrence of service interruption, as long as rendered locally;
- increased data security and privacy.

Despite all these pros, designing edge-based solutions faces important resource-scarcity challenges, for computing, storage, and energy.

These considerations lead to an approach where edge and cloud go hand in hand, coordinated by effective synchronization. Cloud computing (public, hybrid or private) offers valuable centralization capabilities: if all the data are in the same place, any entity in the enterprise can access them where and when needed. Edge allows specific savings and makes the data collected immediately actionable, creating value for applications that gain advantage from real-time analytics, IoT devices and rapid decision-making. The two extremes should be considered as a continuum: “a successful strategy begins with a cohesive plan for managing the data, including both processing and transmission, as well as the overall infrastructure” [28].

In fact, the concept of the computing continuum has been extensively discussed in HiPEAC Vision roadmaps for the last five years, reaching a culmination in the emergence of a new paradigm: the Trans-Continuum, where “edge, fog and cloud computing platforms are being pulled closed together into what will likely become a seamless execution environment”, and where “programming has to be reinvented,

with languages and tools to orchestrate collaborative distributed and decentralized components, as well as components augmented with interface contracts covering both functional and non-functional properties” [29].

The concept of the computing continuum (or, more ambitiously, the Trans-Continuum) is both an enabler for and a requirement of the rest of the KETs in our vision of future CPS enriched with a living dimension. The computing continuum allows the data collected by the system, by means of environmental sensors and/or tactile internet-enhanced human-machine interfaces, to be stored and employed when needed. An integral continuum approach means that individuals can refine their own local rules by running AI at the edge. Conversely, the cloud can re-tune the overall mission tasks and/or individual behaviours based on the information of all the nodes within the swarm to avoid divergence from the global challenge or to adapt to changing conditions.

Towards a new living CPS dimension

Smart everything everywhere is already a reality, given that AI-enabled technologies are embedded in everyday objects. The world is becoming truly collective and connected, increasingly featuring systems that integrate large numbers of multiple interacting components at different scales. In addition, thanks to the tactile internet, it should be possible to change the way humans interact with those systems. Ultimately, the goal of this “internet of everything” is to bring together people, processes, data, and devices.

Classic CPS, powered by AI and the tactile internet, can make substantial steps towards becoming living systems. By definition, living systems are “open, self-organizing systems that have the special

characteristics of life and interact with their environment. This takes place by means of information and material-energy exchanges” [30]. Classic CPS are open by definition due to their ability to actively, and potentially continuously, interact with their environment through sensors and actuators. Additionally, AI can provide CPS with unrivalled understanding capabilities that allow content-rich information exchange, not only with other CPS, but especially with humans.

The introduction of the tactile internet is intended to enable a shift towards enhanced *peer-to-peer relationships and more effective exchanges*, since humans will be capable of interacting with the CPS using their senses and not only through a data/command exchange.

Indeed, as for living systems, the *equilibrium of CPS is dynamic*. CPS are by definition dynamic and reactive systems. The addition of AI and the tactile internet is expected to *dramatically improve the continuously interacting and understanding capabilities* of a CPS, while also unlocking the potential for *evolution and self-organization*. Meanwhile, the ability to *self-organize* is provided by swarm intelligence, which also allows better understanding of the *emergent behaviours* that might arise as an outcome of the *complex dynamics* that will characterize these future CPS. As with natural systems, these dynamics will feature both deterministic and stochastic components.

This evolution will transform a group of highly interconnected smart CPS into something closer to a living computing system, composed of *individuals that are capable of reasoning and communicating with each other to team up and reach overarching goals*. Despite such disruptive potential, this new generation of CPS also throws up new challenges, as discussed below.

Open challenges

Existing challenges in the CPS community, such as modelling, design, architecture, and security issues, are exacerbated by the living, human-centred dimension targeted by the new generation of CPS. Moreover,

these future CPS pose additional challenges related to the self-evolving nature of a heterogeneous society composed of systems and humans, pushing the concept of autonomic systems to the extreme.

Modelling

CPS are hybrid by nature. Their different aspects obey diverse dynamics, including continuous and discrete ones, threatening the established separation of concerns approach. Interactions among aspects are not considered in the models. For instance, traditional application models are basically intended to describe functionalities, disregarding timing aspects or what happens when the application is physically implemented on a given computing platform.

Attempts to capture the dynamic and reactive nature of CPS have been made with respect to adaptivity [31] and timing concerns [32, 33]. However, it is yet to be demonstrated whether and how these attempts would withstand the presence of the additional living dimension, since the swarm effect may affect the model of individual elements. Modelling swarms implies the definition of the local rules, which are always complex, especially when heterogeneous swarms composed of both CPS and humans are to be considered.

The expected human-to-system entanglement in future CPS severely challenges system modelling. Human in the loop, in general, implies an abstract modelling of the human based either on interviews of the operators, employees, etc., or on data from real use. In both cases, more flexible modelling will be needed, to make models evolve over time to fit humans' unpredictable and changeable behaviours.

Architectures

Edge computing is already a key factor when implementing CPS, since flexibility, low energy consumption and high-performance capabilities are already a must. These aspects are even more critical considering the evolution of CPS to include AI, the tactile internet and swarm intelligence.

This evolution forces edge devices to run AI and swarm intelligence algorithms, which normally require the design of

application-specific accelerators to be run on hardware substrates [34]. This strategy still requires manual tuning to comply with target-dependent trade-offs between accuracy, computational complexity, and performance requirements.

Furthermore, as mentioned previously, this evolution also needs to encompass the computing continuum and the tactile internet, which both have tight constraints in terms of communication performance. Therefore, in addition to the challenges of computation, the communication architecture should also be taken into consideration, including mesh networks to improve resiliency and robustness.

Security

The concept of societal security, known as the “*ability of a society to persist in its essential character under changing conditions and possible or actual threats*”, dates back to 1993 and was developed by the Copenhagen School of security studies [35]. As future CPS will form a sort of “society”, security will certainly be a matter of concern for them, as it currently is for any kind of system [36].

Future CPS, exploiting swarm-intelligence-based coordination concepts, will involve non-hierarchical and decentralized control structures that are prone to security issues related to confidentiality, integrity, authentication/identification, and availability [37]. Comprehensive threat modelling, coupled to appropriate mitigation measures to reduce the overall risk or impact of a given threat, is needed both for CPS [38] and for embodied swarm-based systems [37].

Although including the computing continuum forces us to consider security issues along the whole spectrum, it also provides future CPS with strategies to cope with security threats, for example by processing attack-prone data at the edge.

Design

CPS design is already intrinsically complex due to the hybrid and interdisciplinary nature of these systems, which leads to a reliance on partially integrated tool-chains and methodologies tuned for specific

design aspects. Adding the described living dimension will exacerbate such complexity. Indeed, for the described future CPS, it will become essential to consider aspects such as swarm behaviours (local rules, entity cooperation), extremely low latency (required in the tactile internet) and AI decision making (having to deal with both the algorithm definition and its effective porting onto the chosen, potentially constrained, platform).

In this new approach, the idea of humans being part of the system must be considered during every aspect of the design. In addition, the design must address how to communicate and distribute the workload along the computing continuum.

Model checking is an open issue for both classic CPS and embodied swarms of CPS. This is going to be exacerbated for future CPS with humans at the centre, since the presence of humans poses serious challenges in terms of dependability, requiring in turn continuous verification of the system properties with runtime feedback loops to redesign cycles.

To cover all these complex design steps, there are already very good examples of frameworks for CPS design and operation [39] [40], for swarms of CPS design and operation [41], and for porting AI at the edge [42]. Indeed, as for classic CPS, the major issue would be how to get the most from existing frameworks. Interoperability among tools, despite the big promises of meta-model [43] and semantic [44] approaches, is still to be reached, although lately the MLIR initiative [45] seems to have the potential of achieving substantial breakthroughs.

Adaptive and autonomous systems evolution

Leveraging concepts such as the autonomic computing paradigm [46] and related self-* properties [47], classic CPS can achieve self-reconfiguration through awareness of themselves and of their environment [48],[49] by means of feedback control loops [50]. The implementation of the feedback loop at the scale of system of system [51] was attempted through AI-enhanced CPSoS [52]. Nevertheless, this might not suffice for future CPS with

a living dimension, since the self-evolution of the ensemble of individuals would still be limited by design given the fact that, in swarm intelligence, local rules are mostly fixed.

Conclusion

Living CPS appear to be just around the corner. Building on the foundations laid by classic CPS, the key enabling technologies set out in this article will help transform CPS into members of a community, consciously and autonomously cooperating with their human colleagues. Meanwhile, these technologies will help address, at least in part, the challenges that scientists face to make this future a reality.

References

- [1] Yogesh K Dwivedi, Laurie Hughes, Abdullah M Baabdullah, Samuel Ribeiro-Navarrete, Mihalis Giannakis, Mutaz M Al-Debei, Denis Dennehy, Bhimaraya Metri, Dimitrios Buhalis, Christy MK Cheung, et al. 2022. Metaverse beyond the hype: Multidisciplinary perspectives on emerging challenges, opportunities, and agenda for research, practice and policy. *International Journal of Information Management* 66 (2022), 102542.
- [2] K. De Bosschere. AI for a better society. In M. Duranton et al., editors, *HiPEAC Vision 2021*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7092776
- [3] <https://www.nsf.gov/pubs/2017/nsf17529/nsf17529.htm> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [4] Ji Zhou, Yanhong Zhou, Baicun Wang, and Jiyuan Zang. 2019. Human-Cyber-Physical Systems (HCPSs) in the Context of New-Generation Intelligent Manufacturing. *Engineering* 5, 4 (2019), 624–636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eng.2019.07.015>
- [5] <https://www.databridgemarketresearch.com/reports/global-cyber-physical-systems-market> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [6] <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/artificial-intelligence-ai-market> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [7] Jiayang Song, Deyun Lyu, Zhenya Zhang, Zhijie Wang, Tianyi Zhang, and Lei Ma. 2022. When Cyber-Physical Systems Meet AI: A Benchmark, an Evaluation, and a Way Forward. In 44th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering in Practice, ICSE (SEIP) 2022, Pittsburgh, PA, USA, May 22–24, 2022. IEEE, 343–352. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSE-SEIP5303.2022.9794128>
- [8] Yuke Zhu, Ziyu Wang, Josh Merel, Andrei A. Rusu, Tom Erez, Serkan Cabi, Saran Tunyasuvunakool, János Kramár, Raia Hadsell, Nando de Freitas, and Nicolas Heess. 2018. Reinforcement and Imitation Learning for Diverse Visuomotor Skills. In *Robotics: Science and Systems XIV*, Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, USA, June 26–30, 2018, Hadas Kress-Gazit, Siddhartha S. Srinivasa, Tom Howard, and Nikolay Atanasov (Eds.). <https://doi.org/10.15607/RSS.2018.XIV.009>
- [9] Paola Busia, Gianfranco Deriu, Luca Rinelli, Cristina Chesta, Luigi Raffo, and Paolo Meloni. 2022. Target-Aware Neural Architecture Search and Deployment for Keyword Spotting. *IEEE Access* 10 (2022), 40687–40700. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3166939>
- [10] Jinan Fiaidhi, Sabah Mohammed, and Sami Mohammed. 2018. The Robotization of Extreme Automation: The Balance Between Fear and Courage. *IT Prof.* 20, 6 (2018), 87–93. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MITP.2018.2876979>
- [11] L.M.C. Oliveira, R. Dias, C.M. Rebello, M.A.F. Martins, A.E. Rodrigues, A.M. Ribeiro, and I.B.R. Nogueira. 2021. Artificial Intelligence and Cyber-Physical Systems: A Review and Perspectives for the Future in the Chemical Industry. *AI* 2(3) (2021), 429–443. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ai2030027>
- [12] Han Cai, Chuang Gan, Tianzhe Wang, Zhekai Zhang, and Song Han. 2020. Once-for-All: Train One Network and Specialize it for Efficient Deployment. In 8th International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2020, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, April 26–30, 2020. OpenReview.net. <https://openreview.net/forum?id=HyxE1HKwS>
- [13] <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1183457/iot-connected-devices-worldwide/> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [14] <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/techwatch/Pages/tactile-internet.aspx> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [15] Martin Maier, Mahfuzulhoq Chowdhury, Bhaskar Prasad Rimal, and Dung Pham Van. 2016. The tactile internet: vision, recent progress, and open challenges. *IEEE Commun. Mag.* 54, 5 (2016), 138–145. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2016.7470948>
- [16] Nattakorn Promwongsa, Amin Ebrahimzadeh, Diala Naboulsi, Somayeh Kianpisheh, Fatna Belqasmi, Roch H. Glioth, Noël Crespi, and Omar Alfandi. 2021. A Comprehensive Survey of the Tactile Internet: State-of-the-Art and Research Directions. *IEEE Commun. Surv. Tutorials* 23, 1 (2021), 472–523. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2020.3025995>
- [17] Daniel van den Berg, Rebecca Glans, Dorian De Koning, Fernando A. Kuipers, Jochem Lugtenburg, Kurian Polachan, Prabhakar T. Venkata, Chandramani Singh, Belma Turkovic, and Bryan Van Wijk. 2017. Challenges in Haptic Communications Over the Tactile Internet. *IEEE Access* 5 (2017), 23502–23518. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2764181>
- [18] Gerardo Beni and Jing Wang. 1993. *Swarm Intelligence in Cellular Robotic Systems*.
- [19] Mohammad Reza Bonyadi and Zbigniew Michalewicz. 2017. Particle Swarm Optimization for Single Objective Continuous Space Problems: A Review. *Evolutionary Computation* 25 (2017), 1–54.
- [20] Vincent T’kindt, Nicolas Monmarché, Fabrice Tercinet, and Daniel Läutig. 2002. An Ant Colony Optimization algorithm to solve a 2-machine bicriteria flowshop scheduling problem. *Eur. J. Oper. Res.* 142, 2 (2002), 250–257. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-2217\(02\)00265-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-2217(02)00265-5)
- [21] <http://apium.com/> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [22] <https://www.swarmfarm.com/> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [23] <https://www.marketdataforecast.com/market-reports/swarm-intelligence-market> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [24] <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/swarm-intelligence-market> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [25] Melanie Schranz, Gianni A. Di Caro, Thomas Schmickl, Wilfried Elmenreich, Farshad Arvin, Y. Ahmet Sekercioglu, and Micha Sende. 2021. Swarm Intelligence and cyber-physical systems: Concepts, challenges and future trends. *Swarm Evol. Comput.* 60 (2021), 100762. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.swevo.2020.100762>
- [26] <https://blogs.idc.com/2020/06/01/edge-computing-not-all-edges-are-created-equal/> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [27] <https://www.gartner.com/smarterwithgartner/what-edge-computing-means-for-infrastructure-and-operations-leaders> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [28] <https://www.techtarget.com/searchcio/DrivingITSuccess/4-Things-You-Need-to-Know-Now>About-Edge-Computing> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [29] M. Duranton, M. Malm, and M. Ostasz. The continuum of computing. In M. Duranton et al., editors, *HiPEAC Vision 2021*, pages 40–43, Jan 2021.
- [30] James G. Miller. 1965. Living systems: Basic concepts. *Behavioral Science* 10, 3 (1965), 193–237. 10.1002/bs.3830100302
- [31] Karol Desnos, Maxime Pelcat, Jean-François Nezan, Shuvra S. Bhattacharyya, and Slaheddine Aridhi. 2013. PiMM: Parameterized and Interfaced dataflow Meta-Model for MPSoCs runtime reconfiguration. In 2013 International Conference on Embedded Computer Systems: Architectures, Modeling, and Simulation, SAMOS 2013, Agios Konstantinos, Samos Island, Greece, July 15–18, 2013. IEEE, 41–48. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SAMOS.2013.6621104>
- [32] Marten Lohstroh. 2020. *Reactors: A Deterministic Model of Concurrent Computation for Reactive Systems*. Ph.D. Dissertation. University of California, Berkeley, USA. <https://www.escholarship.org/uc/item/0fm2m3k1>
- [33] Marten Lohstroh, Christian Menard, Alexander Schulz-Rosengarten, Matthew Weber, Jerónimo Castrillón, and Edward A. Lee. 2020. A Language for Deterministic Coordination Across Multiple Timelines. In Forum for Specification and Design Languages, FDL 2020, Kiel, Germany, September 15–17, 2020. IEEE, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1109/FDL50818.2020.9232939>
- [34] Yechan Yu, HoJin Kim, Jinjoo Ha, Daewoo Kim, and Kang Yi. 2018. Cost-Performance Comparison of Various Accelerator Implementation Platforms for Deep Convolutional Neural Network. In *Parallel and Distributed Computing, Applications and Technologies*, 19th International Conference, PDCAT 2018, Jeju Island, South Korea, August 20–22, 2018, Revised Selected Papers (Communications in Computer and Information Science), Jong Hyuk Park, Hong Shen, Yunsick Sung, and Hui Tian (Eds.), Vol. 931. Springer, 335–344. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-5907-1_36
- [35] Waever, Ole, Barry Buzan, Morten Kelstrup, and Pierre Lemaitre (1993). *Identity, Migration and the New Security Agenda in Europe*. Pinter Publishers
- [36] <https://time.com/5868008/twitter-hack-accounts-targeted-bitcoin-scam/> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [37] Liqun Chen and Siaw-Lynn Ng. 2022. Securing emergent behaviour in swarm robotics. *J. Inf. Secur. Appl.* 64 (2022), 103047. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisa.2021.103047>
- [38] Jean-Paul A. Yaacoub, Ola Salman, Hassan N. Noura, Nesrine Kaaniche, Ali Chehab, and Mohamad Malli. 2020. Cyber-physical systems security: Limitations, issues and future trends. *Microprocessors and Microsystems* 77 (2020), 103201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpro.2020.103201>
- [39] <https://www.cerberoh2020.eu/toolchain/> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [40] <https://into-cps.org/> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [41] <https://www.cpswarm.eu/index.php/cpswarm-workbench/> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [42] <https://www.aloha-h2020.eu/> [Last access on 22/11/2022]

- [43] Felice Balarin, Yosinori Watanabe, Harry Hsieh, Luciano Lavagno, Claudio Passerone, and Alberto Sangiovanni-Vincentelli. 2003. Metropolis: An Integrated Electronic System Design Environment. *Computer* 36, 4 (apr 2003), 45–52. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2003.1193228>
- [44] Peter Gorm Larsen, John S. Fitzgerald, Jim Woodcock, Carl Gamble, Richard John Payne, and Kenneth Pierce. 2017. Features of Integrated Model-Based Co-modelling and Co-simulation Technology. In *Software Engineering and Formal Methods - SEFM 2017 Collocated Workshops: DataMod, FAACS, MSE, CoSim-CPS, and FOCLASA*, Trento, Italy, September 4-5, 2017, Revised Selected Papers (Lecture Notes in Computer Science), Antonio Cerone and Marco Roveri (Eds.), Vol. 10729. Springer, 377–390. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-74781-1_26
- [45] <https://mlir.lvm.org/> [Last access on 22/11/2022]
- [46] Jeffrey O. Kephart and David M. Chess. 2003. The Vision of Autonomic Computing. *Computer* 36, 1 (2003), 41–50. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2003.1160055>
- [47] Enterprise Management Associate. 2006. Practical Autonomic Computing: Roadmap to Self Managing Technology. White Paper (2006). <https://www.enterprisemanagement.com/research/asset.php/286/Practical-Autonomic-Computing--Roadmap-to-Self-Managing-Technology>
- [48] Frank D. Macías-Escrivá, Rodolfo Haber, Raul del Toro, and Vicente Hernandez. 2013. Self-adaptive systems: A survey of current approaches, research challenges and applications. *Expert Systems with Applications* 40, 18 (2013), 7267–7279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2013.07.033>
- [49] Francesca Palumbo, Tiziana Fanni, Carlo Sau, Alfonso Rodríguez, Daniel Madroñal, Karol Desnos, Antoine Morvan, Maxime Pelcat, Claudio Rubattu, Raquel Lazzano, Luigi Raffo, Eduardo de la Torre, Eduardo Juárez, César Sanz, and Pablo Sanchez de Rojas. 2019. Hardware/Software Self-adaptation in CPS: The CERBERO Project Approach. In *Embedded Computer Systems: Architectures, Modeling, and Simulation - 19th International Conference, SAMOS 2019, Samos, Greece, July 7-11, 2019, Proceedings (Lecture Notes in Computer Science)*, Dionisios N. Pnevmatikatos, Maxime Pelcat, and Matthias Jung (Eds.), Vol. 11733. Springer, 416–428. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-27562-4_30
- [50] Éric Rutten, Nicolas Marchand, and Daniel Simon. 2013. Feedback Control as MAPE-K Loop in Autonomic Computing. In *Software Engineering for Self-Adaptive Systems III. Assurances - International Seminar, Dagstuhl Castle, Germany, December 15-19, 2013, Revised Selected and Invited Papers (Lecture Notes in Computer Science)*, Rogério de Lemos, David Garlan, Carlo Ghezzi, and Holger Giese (Eds.), Vol. 9640. Springer, 349–373. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-74183-3_12
- [51] Georgios Keramidas, Christos P. Antonopoulos, Nikolaos S. Voros, Pekka Jääskeläinen, Marisa Catalán Cid, Evangelia I. Zacharaki, Apostolos P. Fournaris, and Aris S. Lalos. 2020. CPSoSaware: Cross-Layer Cognitive Optimization Tools & Methods for the Lifecycle Support of Dependable CPSoS. In *2020 IEEE Computer Society Annual Symposium on VLSI, ISVLSI 2020, Limassol, Cyprus, July 6-8, 2020*. IEEE, 470–475. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISVLSI49217.2020.00-12>
- [52] Stavros Nousias, Nikos Piperigkos, Gerasimos Arvanitis, Apostolos P. Fournaris, Aris S. Lalos, and Konstantinos Moustakas. 2021. Empowering cyberphysical systems of systems with intelligence. *CoRR abs/2107.02264* (2021). arXiv:2107.02264 <https://arxiv.org/abs/2107.02264>

Francesca Palumbo is an associate professor at Università degli Studi di Sassari, Italy.

Raquel Lazzano is a research assistant at Università degli Studi di Sassari, Italy.

Daniel Madroñal is a research assistant at Università degli Studi di Sassari, Italy.

This document is part of the HiPEAC Vision available at hipeac.net/vision.

This is release v.1, January 2023.

Cite as: F. Palumbo, R. Lazzano and D. Madroñal. Towards a living dimension: The future of cyber-physical systems. In M. Duranton et al., editors, *HiPEAC Vision 2023*, pages 44-53, Jan 2023.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7461786

The HiPEAC project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 871174.

© HiPEAC 2023

